

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Grass2Algae

From grass juices to the cultivation of microalgae

The Grass2Algae operational group aims to evaluate the use of grass juice for growing microalgae as an additional source of income for farmers.

Main challenge

Flemish Farmers have access to an abundance of roadside grass or low-quality grass that cannot be used as animal feed.

Grass2Algae solution

Grass juice accounts for 40-60% of the total grass weight and is an excellent source of nutrients, being rich in macro and micronutrients that are necessary for the growth of microalgae.

Valorisation process

The grass juice is firstly separated from the fibers through a pressing step. Then microalgae is cultivated using the grass juice as growing medium.

Results

- The juice from cultivated grass clippings may be used as a nutrient source in the production of protein-rich microalgae biomass.
- The acidity of the juice may warrant the need to artificially increase the pH of the culture medium for optimal growth of the microalgae and reduce the microbial load during cultivation.
- Future (pilot-scale) studies are needed to further explore the potential of using grass juice as a nutrient source for microalgal growth.

Algae cultivation installation

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our journey!

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